

**INCREASING ENERGY EFFICIENCY TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS
OF CABLE PRODUCTS LLC “NATIONAL HOLDINGS”**

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Annotation. The article presents the results on the development and creation of energy-saving technology that ensures the efficient operation of asynchronous electric drives with high energy performance on the basis of modern semiconductor technology, taking into account the production characteristics of LLC “NATIONAL HOLDINGS”.

Key words: asynchronous electric drive, frequency converter, dynamic mode, electromechanical system, electric drive control system.

Аннотация. В статье приводятся результаты по разработке и созданию энергосберегающей технологии, обеспечивающей эффективную работу асинхронного электропривода волочильной машины с высокими энергетическими показателями на базе современной полупроводниковой техники, с учетом производственных особенностей ООО “NATIONAL HOLDINGS”.

Ключевые слова: асинхронный электропривод, частотный преобразователь, динамический режим, электромеханическая система, система управления электроприводом.

Аннотация. Мақолада “NATIONAL HOLDINGS” МЧЖни ишлаб чиқариш хусусиятларини ҳисобга олган ҳолда замонавий яримўтказгич технологияси асосида юқори энергия кўрсаткичларига эга бўлган асинхрон электр юритмаларининг самарали ишлашини таъминлайдиган энергия тежайдиган технологияни ишлаб чиқиш ва яратиш бўйича натижалар келтирилган.

Калит сўзлар: асинхрон электр юритма, частота ўзгарткичи, динамик режим, электромеханик тизим, электр юритмани бошқариш тизими.

In the context of an ever-growing energy crisis, the rational use of energy resources and electrical energy is an urgent problem, therefore the development, research and widespread implementation of energy-saving technologies and devices is an urgent task for today and the entire subsequent period [1].

In the world, by improving the dynamic operating modes of technological machines and mechanisms, elements of the electromechanical system with modern control devices, improving the elements of the electromechanical system, and using control methods, energy-efficient technologies are created in various industries. At the same time, by increasing the energy efficiency of industrial installations and improving control systems for electric drives, work is being carried out to reduce electrical energy consumption and, in turn, special attention is paid to the development of this industry. As is known, the bulk of industrial, agricultural and household facilities are driven by unregulated electric drives of mass use, consuming from 60 to 70% of all electrical energy consumed by electrical installations. Of the total number of electric drives for industrial mechanisms, only a small part of the objects have a complex and finely controlled technological process for which an adjustable electric drive is used [2].

The vast majority of these mechanisms are uncontrolled and non-automated; the installed power of the actuators, due to the provision of starting modes, is on average 1.5 - 3 times more than the actually required power. This paper provides

recommendations for improving the energy efficiency of cable production in LLC “NATIONAL HOLDINGS”. To ensure improved energy performance, it is most advisable to equip the electric drive with a frequency converter. As a converter, it is proposed to choose a modern frequency converter with pulse width modulation (PWM). Since this type of frequency converters is the most promising due to its more stable energy performance and high-power factor. Modern frequency converters with PWM have an efficiency and a power factor of at least 0.97. In addition, frequency converters with PWM are also available without a matching transformer, which significantly improves its energy, operational and weight-size characteristics.

For the electric drive of electrical equipment, the most suitable, from our point of view, is the Toshiba converter, the diagram of which is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. AC frequency converter circuit.

According to the method of controlling an electric motor, frequency converters (FCs) can be divided into two groups: with vector and scalar control, and each method has its own advantages and disadvantages [3].

Scalar control type. With scalar (frequency) control, harmonic currents of the motor phases are formed, which means that control is most often maintained at a constant ratio of the maximum motor torque to the resistance moment on the shaft. That is, when the frequency changes, the voltage amplitude changes in such a way that the ratio of the maximum motor torque to the current load torque remains unchanged.

This ratio is called the overload capacity of the motor. At constant overload capacity, the rated power factor and efficiency of the engine over the entire range of rotation speed control practically do not change.

An important advantage of the scalar method is the ability to simultaneously control a group of electric motors.

The scalar control method allows for easy adjustment, even when using factory settings.

Vector control type. Vector control is a method of controlling synchronous and asynchronous motors, which not only generates harmonic currents (voltages) of the phases, but also provides control of the rotor magnetic flux (torque on the motor shaft).

Vector control is used when during operation the load can change at the same frequency, i.e. there is no clear relationship between the load torque and the rotation speed, and also in cases where it is necessary to obtain an extended frequency control range at rated torques, for example, 0...50 Hz for a torque of 100% or even for a short time 150-200% of M_{nom} , this allows you to significantly increase control range, control accuracy, increase the speed of the electric drive. This method provides direct control of motor torque. The torque is determined by the stator current, which creates an exciting magnetic field.

With direct torque control, it is necessary to change, in addition to the amplitude and phase of the stator current, that is, the current vector. This is where the term “vector control” comes from. The vector method of controlling a frequency converter allows for much better control of the electric motor than the scalar method. But setting up such a converter requires deep knowledge in the field of electric drive design and electrical machines.

Vector control method with speed feedback - used for precision control (it is necessary to use an incremental encoder) of speed, when during operation the load can change at the same frequency, i.e. there is no clear relationship between load torque and rotation speed, and also in cases where a maximum frequency control range is required at torques close to the nominal one.

The vector method works normally if the engine's nameplate values are entered correctly and its auto test has successfully passed. The vector method is implemented through complex real-time calculations performed by the converter processor based on information about the output current, frequency and voltage.

The processor also uses information about the passport characteristics of the engine, which is entered by the user. The response time of the converter to a change in the output current (load torque) is 50...200 ms. The vector method allows you to minimize the reactive current of the motor when reducing the load by adequately reducing the voltage on the motor. If the load on the motor shaft increases, the converter adequately increases the voltage on the motor. In addition, for direct torque control at low, close to zero rotation speeds, operation of a frequency-controlled electric drive without speed feedback is impossible. Vector control with a speed feedback sensor provides a control range of up to 1:1000 and higher, speed control accuracy is hundredths of a percent, torque accuracy is a few percent.

In this case, it is advisable to use vector control for the drive. Connecting the electric drive to the network "directly" leads to the fact that 6–10 times the starting currents flow through the windings, which lead to the emergence of large electrodynamic and mechanical forces, as a result of which the motor windings are subject to increased wear, the service life of the mechanical and electrical components is significantly reduced parts of electric drive and mechanism.

After reaching a steady rotation speed, the electric drive operates in underload mode, as a result of which there is an unreasonable overconsumption of the total power consumed, as a result of which the technical, economic, energy and operational indicators of the installation as a whole are reduced. At the same time, the specific energy consumption per unit of production increases.

To reduce the magnitude of starting currents of asynchronous motors and increase the energy efficiency of an automated electric drive in steady-state operating modes with a relatively low degree of load on the mechanisms, it is necessary to optimize

energy parameters according to various optimality criteria (minimum stator current, maximum efficiency and power factor).

The mechanical and electromechanical characteristics of the motor were calculated and plotted using the Mathcad 2000 program. As a result of the simulation, we obtain the following characteristics of the frequency converter - asynchronous motor system (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Calculated waveforms of the frequency converter - asynchronous motor system.

Fig. 3. Engine speed transient graph

Optimization of energy parameters for asynchronous electric drives can be realized using the “Thyristor voltage regulator-induction motor” system with microprocessor control.

The use of a thyristor voltage regulator when implementing an automated electric drive also makes it possible to increase the functionality of the system, both in static and dynamic operating modes. The use of a microprocessor control system ensures, while maintaining the constancy of the structure of the automated electric drive, the implementation of the selected criterion for the optimality of the energy parameters of the system, ensuring a smooth start and effective protection against emergency operating conditions.

Based on the above, it can be stated that the development and creation of energy-saving technology that ensures the operation of asynchronous electric drives with high energy performance based on modern semiconductor technology, taking into account the production features of NATIONAL HOLDINGS LLC, is one of the pressing problems, and the development, research and the creation of new generation energy-saving technologies that best meet modern requirements for technological drawing machines from an energy point of view is an urgent object of research.

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